

WITCH HAZEL : TRADITIONAL REMEDY ON MODERN SKIN CARE.

ABSTRACT: Witch hazel (*Hamamelis virginiana*) is a plant native to North America, renowned for its potent medicinal properties, particularly in skin and wound care. The “witch hazel” name is derived from old English word “wych”, meaning “bendable” referring to the plants flexible branches. This article explores the biochemical composition and therapeutic potential of witch hazel, emphasizing its role as a natural remedy in contemporary dermatology. By considering the plant's rich history and traditional uses, we examine how modern scientific research supports and expands upon these applications. The article also discusses the potential of witch hazel in innovative dermatological treatments and its relevance in the growing field of natural and sustainable skincare. Also witch hazel has the antioxidant properties and anticancer properties, making it a promising natural remedy for cancer prevention and treatment. It is a blessing in medicinal field and as well as it is promoting health and well-being. Its unique combination of beauty and utility has made it subject of interest in both horticulture and natural medicine. The enduring appeal of witch hazel lies in its natural origin and versatility, making it a cherished component in both traditional and modern herbal remedies. Beyond the medicinal uses witch hazel has symbolic significance in various cultures often associated with protection, healing and purification. Despite its widespread uses it is generally considered as safe for most people, though some may experience mild irritation according to their skin type. It was traditionally used by Native American tribes not only for its healing properties but also in rituals and as a tool dowsing, a method for locating underground water sources. Through this comprehensive analysis, we aim to highlight the unique properties of witch hazel, positioning it as a valuable and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic skincare products.

INTRODUCTION:

Fig. 1 : Witch Hazel

Hamamelis Virginiana, a member of the family Hamamelidaceae indigenous to damp woods on Atlantic coast of north America regionally from Florida to Nova scotia and may be found as far west as Texas. The appearance structure of the plant and leaves vary widely with no consistent pattern of variation or geographical correlation. The plant may be a all shrub with the branches coming from the base or small tree of up to 4.6 m tall. The leaves are 1 to 5 cm long and may alternate or stipulate, have short petals, and may be inequilateral or rhomboid-ovate, with an oblique base and sinuation sinuate dentate margin. The flower golden – yellow color dentate margin.^[2]

History: When European settlers arrived in North America, they observed the ingenious use of witch hazel and quickly adopted it into their own medicinal practices. The healing properties and its effectiveness in treating skin conditions in general astringent, made it valuable remedy in the settlers herbal medicine cabinets .The commercial history of witch hazel started at 19th century. In mid of 1800s , the plant's medicinal properties caught by the attention of American entrepreneurs, particularly in New England. One of the most remarkable person at that period was Thomas Newton Dickinson who started producing witch hazel extract commercially in 1866 in Connecticut i.e., U.S state in southern New England that has a mix coastal and rural areas dotted with small towns. His company , T.N.Dickinson's , became one of the first to market witch hazel as a household remedy, and the Dickinson brand remains identity of witch hazel products today. It have been also said that the indigenous origins the witch hazel is native to north America and its use dates back centuries among Indigenous and Cherokee. They utilized the plant for its medicinal properties ,creating soft or moist liquid extract made by boiling plant or herbal material in water to dissolve the chemical materials from the bark and leaves to treat the slash and skin irritation , inflammation and tumors . It was also used as a natural astringent and to soothe sore muscles. Cultural and folk practices beyond its medicinal uses, witch hazel has also played a role in various cultural practices. In particular ,it was used in dowsing ,a traditionally practice where practitioners used a forked witch hazel branch to locate the underground resources – a practice that persists in some rural areas to this day. In summary ,witch hazel has a rich history that spans from its indigenous roots in North America to its widespread use in modern skin care and traditional medicine. Its continued popularity is a testament to its continuation popularity is a testament to its enduring effectiveness as a natural remedy.^[3]

Biological source: Witch hazel thrives in moist, well-drained soils and is commonly found in woodland areas, along streams, and in shady spots. It is adaptable to different soil types, making it a resilient plant in its native range. The witch hazel is easy to identify as its biological significance said that it classify as "shrub," it does not usually top 4.5 m (15') in height. The exceptional species of this tree found in Bed ford, that was found to be 10.5 m (35 ft) tall with a trunk nearly half a meter in diameter. They absorb light that escapes the covering trees with their twisted ,unsymmetrical branches ,which forms a spread irregularly crow Witch hazel leaves are also clearly different from others and therefore easy to recognize; 7.6-15.2 cm (3-6") long, they are broadly elliptical and edged with rounded teeth or lobes. The leaves tend to be much larger in the northern part of its range. The witch hazel flowers are open, when the leaves are turning and falling, because it's very unusual in appearance, they have four crumpled-looking, strap-like yellow petals and release a delicate fragrance.Witch hazel is also found in moist woods throughout the region of estern US, from Florida extending into Canada also found in central Texas and southern Missouri and collected near pump house.^[4]

Microscopy: 1984, Photo Micrography George J. Wilder viewed radial section of wood of witch hazel. The microscopic structure of wood consists of various cell types. Tracheid's vessels and fibers make up the majority of wood cells. Tracheid's are dead, hollow cells that transport water and minerals. Vessels are larger, more open cells that also transport water and nutrients. Fibers are smaller, thicker cells that provide strength and support. Ray cells are horizontal cells that store food and nutrients. Parenchyma cells are living cells that store starch and oils.^[5]

1. **Stigma:** Is an important part of the plant's life cycle. Without it, the plant would not be able reproduce. The stigma is a vital component of the plant's survival, and it is a unique plant with a special stigma with reproductive process is fascinating. The stigma is a key factor in the plant's ability to thrive of the stigma is a remarkable feature and it's allows the plant to produce seeds and propagate and the stigma is a crucial part of the plant's biology, so this plant that continues to fascinate scientists.^[5]
2. **Leaf surface:** Colored scanning electron micrograph of the upper surface of a witch-hazel leaf. Veins are branch across the surface are grey in color. These contain xylem and phloem, which conduct water and nutrients throughout the leaf. The star- shaped structure is a hair cell or trichome. The blade of the leaf is formed of a layer of epidermal cells (green), among which are stomata (leaf pores, white). These are the sites of gaseous exchange. Witch-hazel is used in herbal medicine to treat sprains, burns and skin inflammation.^[5]
3. **Fruit:** The microscopic structure of the witch hazel fruit has interesting features that are characteristic of its reproductive system, from details we predict that, fruit type of the witch hazel is a woody capsule, which is about 1 cm long. It typically contains two seeds, each within its own chamber (locule) Exocarp has the outermost layer of the fruit, the exocarp, consists of thick-walled cells. These cells are designed to protect the inner tissues and seeds, giving the fruit its tough, woody exterior.^[5]

Parts of Witch hazel which has cosmetic values – [6]

Table 1 :- Parts of Witch Hazel and its uses;

Parts	Uses
Leaves of witch hazel	To make ointment for skin softening, Paste masks, Bath preparations, after shave lotion, Face powders etc
Bark	Making cream for inflamed skin and Baby shampoos, Bubble bath Eye lotion, Hair conditioning, Lipstick, Deodorants, Foundations, Moisturizing agents etc.
Twigs	Whiteheads, pimples, oily skin and indoor tanning preparations, Skin freshening, Hair conditioners etc
Roots	Itching to skin in lotion
Flower	Eye lotion, blusher, cleansing for face and neck, bath oils

GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION

Witch hazel is a flowering shrub native to North America. Major distribution centres are Asia, Europe, Malaysia region but also extends into Australia, Tropical and Southern Africa, and Madagascar. Several species are found in different region.^[8]

North America: The most common species, *Hamamelis virginiana* is native to the eastern United States and parts of Canada. It grows in deciduous forests, along streams, and in areas with well-drained soil from Nova Scotia down to Texas and Florida.^[8]

Asian Species: Ranges in native Japan particularly in the mountainous regions of Honshu and Hokkaido. Found in mixed forests, often on slopes and in valleys where the soil is well drained but retains moisture. This species found in Japan is named as *Hamamelis Japonica*.^[8]

Europe Species: Though not native, witch hazel has been cultivated in Europe, particularly in gardens and parks. *Hamamelis intermedia* is a popular hybrid in European horticulture, developed from the Japanese and Chinese species.^[8]

Overall, Witch hazel grow in temperate regions with cool climates, often in woodland environments with moist, well-drained soil.^[8]

COLLECTION & CULTIVATION:

Cultivating witch hazel (*Hamamelis*) requires specific environmental conditions and care practices to ensure healthy growth and vibrant flowering. Here's a detailed guide on how to successfully cultivate witch hazel:^[7]

Site Selection:

- Sunlight:** Witch hazel thrives in full sun. While it can tolerate some shade, more sunlight generally results in better flowering. In hotter climates, providing afternoon shade can help prevent leaf scorch.^[7]
- Soil:** Witch hazel prefers well-drained soils that are rich in organic matter. The soil should be slightly acidic to neutral, with a pH range of 5.5 to 7.0. It can tolerate sandy or clay soils if they are well-drained.^[7]
- Moisture:** Witch hazel plants require consistently moist soil, especially during the growing season. They are not tolerant of drought, particularly when young, so regular watering is essential. However, the soil should not be waterlogged, as this can lead to root rot.^[7]

Planting:

- Timing:** The best time to plant witch hazel is in the spring or fall when temperatures are cooler, and the plant is not actively growing. This allows the plant to establish its root system before the heat of summer or the cold of winter.^[9]

- Planting Method:** Dig a hole that is twice as wide and as deep as the root ball of the plant. If the soil is heavy clay or very sandy, mix in organic matter like compost to improve drainage and nutrient content. Place the plant in the hole, ensuring that the top of the root ball is level with the surrounding soil. Backfill the hole with soil, gently firming it around the base of the plant. Water thoroughly after planting to help settle the soil and eliminate air pockets.^[9]

Fertilization:

- Fertilizer Type:** Witch hazel is not a heavy feeder, but it benefits from an annual application of balanced, slow-release fertilizer.^[10]
- Application Timing:** Apply fertilizer in early spring, just before new growth begins. If the soil is rich in organic matter, additional fertilization may not be necessary.^[10]

Pruning:

- Purpose:** Pruning is essential for maintaining the shape of the plant, encouraging air circulation, and removing dead or damaged wood.^[10]
- Timing:** The best time to prune witch hazel is in late spring or early summer, immediately after flowering. This prevents cutting off next year's flower buds, which form on old wood.^[10]

Method of pruning -

- Shaping:** Lightly trim the branches to maintain a natural shape. Avoid heavy pruning, as witch hazel has a slow growth rate.^[10]
- Thinning:** Remove any crossing or rubbing branches to improve air circulation within the canopy. This also helps prevent fungal diseases.^[10]
- Deadwood:** Cut away any dead, damaged, or diseased branches. Make clean cuts just above a healthy bud or branch junction.^[10]

PHYTO-sCONSTITUENTS: ^[11]

Table 2 :- Phytoconstituents with composition and amount;

Class	Composition	Amount
Phenolic acids	4-hydroxybenzoic acid	2.68 µg/g
	Vanillin	0.11 µg/g
	Vanillic acid	0.87 µg/g
	Protocatechuric acid	0.56 µg/g
	Methyl gallate	0.07 µg/g
	Ferulic acid	0.45 µg/g
	Ellagic acid	76.00 ug/g
Flavonoids	Naringenin	0.22 ug/g
	Quercetin-3-O-glucoside	0.56 ug/g
	Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside	0.56 ug/g
Flavan-3-ols (catechins)	Catechin(free)	143.30 ug/g
	Epicatechin(free)	0.67 ug/g
	Total flavanols monomers	230.13 ug/g
	Gallocatechin(free)	76.44 ug/g

	Epigallocatechin(free)	0.67 ug/g
Gallotannins	Hamamelitannin	2910.21 ug/g
Procyanidins dimers	Procyanidin B1	18.03 ug/g
	Procyanidin B2	0.00 ug/g
	Total procyanidins dimers	18.08 ug/g
Oligomeric and polymeric proanthocyanidins	Catechin	
	Epicatechin	221.53 ug/g
	Gallocatechin	13.79 ug/g
	Epigallocatechin	127.79 ug/g
	Catechin Gallate + Epicatechin	2.46 ug/g
		9.03 ug/g

COSMETIC USES OF WITCH HAZEL:

Soothing Irritation

- Anti-Inflammatory Properties:** Witch hazel contains tannins, which are polyphenolic compounds known for their anti-inflammatory effects. These tannins help reduce redness, swelling, and discomfort in irritated skin, making witch hazel beneficial for conditions like eczema and dermatitis.^[12]
- Application:** For soothing irritated skin, apply witch hazel extract to the affected area using a cotton ball. It can be used several times a day, depending on the severity of the irritation.^[12]

Anti-Acne Properties

- Astringent Effects:** Witch hazel's astringent qualities help tighten the skin and reduce the size of pores. This action helps to control excess oil production, which can contribute to acne.^[12]
- Antibacterial Action:** The extract also has mild antibacterial properties that help to cleanse the skin and prevent bacterial growth, which is crucial in managing acne.^[12]
- Usage:** Use witch hazel as a toner by applying it to a clean face after washing. It can help remove residual oil and impurities, contributing to clearer skin.^[12]

Reducing Dark Circles

- Improves Circulation:** Witch hazel enhances blood flow, which can help reduce the appearance of dark circles under the eyes. Better circulation helps to clear out excess fluids and improve the skin's overall appearance.^[12]
- Tightening Effect:** The astringent nature of witch hazel helps to tighten the delicate skin around the eyes, which can reduce puffiness and give a more refreshed look.^[12]
- Application:** Dab witch hazel gently around the eyes with a cotton pad, being careful not to get it into the eyes. Regular use can improve the appearance of dark circles and puffiness.^[12]

Relieving Sunburn

- Cooling Sensation:** The extract provides a cooling effect when applied to sunburned skin, which can alleviate the burning sensation associated with overexposure to the sun.^[12]
- Reduces Inflammation:** Witch hazel helps to decrease inflammation and redness caused by sunburn. The astringent properties can also aid in reducing the peeling that often follows a sunburn.^[12]

3. **Application:** Apply witch hazel directly to the sunburned area using a soft cloth or cotton ball. Avoid using it on broken skin or severe burns; in such cases, seek medical attention.^[12]

Managing Oily Skin

1. **Balances Oil Production:** Regular use of witch hazel can help regulate oil production, making it a good option for individuals with oily skin. By tightening pores and reducing excess oil, it helps to maintain a matte complexion.^[13]
2. **Non-Comedogenic:** Witch hazel does not clog pores, making it suitable for those prone to acne. It can help manage oil without causing additional breakouts.^[13]
3. **Application:** Use witch hazel as a daily toner. Apply it to your face after cleansing to help control oil and refine the skin's texture.^[13]

Enhancing Skin Tone and Texture

1. **Improves Skin Texture:** The astringent properties of witch hazel can help tighten and firm the skin, leading to a smoother texture. This can be beneficial for reducing the appearance of fine lines and uneven skin texture.^[13]
2. **Brightening Effect:** Regular use may help to brighten the skin by promoting a more even tone and reducing the appearance of blemishes and discoloration.^[13]

Treatment of Razor Burn

1. **Calms Irritation:** Witch hazel can be used to soothe skin irritation caused by shaving. It helps reduce redness and inflammation, making it a good aftershave treatment.^[13]
2. **Antiseptic Properties:** The extract has mild antiseptic properties that help prevent infection in areas that have been recently shaved or are prone to ingrown hairs.^[13]

Overall, witch hazel is a versatile and natural skincare ingredient that can benefit various skin concerns. It's essential to use it appropriately and monitor your skin's reaction to ensure it works well for your individual needs.^[13]

ADVERSE EFFECTS OF WITCH HAZEL-

Witch hazel contains a cancer causing chemicals (safrole), but in amounts that are too small to be of concern. It might cause stomach upset when taken by mouth. Liver problems can be occur due to large doses.^[14]

MARKETED FORMULATION:

Fig 2. Witch Hazel Moisturizer

Product Name: Witch hazel moisturizer ^[15]

Brand name: Jovees herbal

Product details: It nutritious the skin naturally. It rapidly absorbs because it contains emollients derived from witch hazel, coconut, Aloe vera, jojoba and chamomile that replenish your body with gentle touch

Benefits: Nutritious the skin with gentle touch

How to use: Apply sufficient quantity on face and neck.

Ingredients: Witch hazel extract, aloe vera extract, chamomile extract, wheatgerm oil olive oil, honey, rose water

Price: 316 Rs

Size: 200g

Best before: 36 months from Manufacturing

Fig 3. Witch Hazel Cream

Product Name: Witch hazel cream (Also known as hazel cream)^[19]

Brand name: Medisynth

Product Details: Witch hazel is best known in homeopathic practice. It has been tasted and used for several generations for the care and protection for sensitive skin. It is used as sunscreen to protect the skin from sunburn and its regular use helps to lighten sunburnt and over- exposed skin. It helps to quickly heal damaged blood vessel, clearing spots, blotches, acne and warts.

This cream is completely free from toxic, allergic or side effects and it is absolutely safe.

Uses: Acne spots and warts, aging sign, tones and skin, skin cleanser, cuts and wound, eye bags.

Ingredients: *Hamamelis Virginica* extract, *calendula officinalis* extract.

How to use: Use twice a day. Take in small quantity and massage gently.

Price: 91Rs

Fig 4. Witch hazel hydrating and pore minimizing toner

Product Name: Witch hazel hydrating and pore minimizing toner^[16]

Brand name: The skin toner

Product details: Hydrating and pore minimizing toner not only acts as an astringent but it also hydrates your skin. This is rich in aloe vera to soothe any inflammation on your skin, controls oil and keeps acne away. It is suitable for sensitive skin. It is alcoholic free and safe for skin.

Benefits: Help to make skin tighter, it cleanses pores, controls oil, provide hydration and maintain ph balance

- It is alcoholic free
- it is environment friendly

Ingredients: Witch hazel, aloe vera, pomegranate

Price: 211Rs

Fig 5. Witch hazel mist spray

Product Name: Witch hazel mist spray^[17]

Brand name: Neud

Product details: It is used for instant fix for tired, dull and dehydrating face.it works great for various skin conditions related to irritation and inflammation. It is made up of peppermint and neem which gives your skin a calming and soothing effect.

Ingredients: witch hazel extract, neem extract, mint oil, aloe vera extract, allantone, zinc PCA, oxynex ST liquid, sodium gluconate, sodium benzoate, potassium sorbate, organic glycerine, fragrance, aqua.

Uses:

Price: 239rs

Quantity: 100ml

Self life: 24 months

Fig 6. Pore protecting toner

Product name: Pore protecting toner^[20]

Brand name: Dickinsons

Product details: Specially formulated to address common skin care concerns, this toner is the ultimate solution for those seeking clear, radiant skin. A natural astringent helps to minimize pores, reduce redness, removes excess oil, dirt and impurities.

Ingredients: Hamamelis virginiana water, grain alcohol, witch hazel extract

Use: For skin glow, soothing, antimicrobial controlling, and antioxidant

Price: 1499 Rs

Quantity: In different quantity available.

HOME MADE REMEDIES OF WITCH HAZEL-

1. **Soothing compress:** Soak a clean cloth in witch hazel and apply it to areas of irritation or inflammation such as minor skin rashes or insect bites, for relief.^[21]
2. **Eye soother:** Place a few drops of witch hazel on a cotton ball and gently apply it to tired or puffy eyes to help reduce Toner: Mix equal parts witch and water to create a soothing facial toner. Apply with a cotton pad to help with acne and tighten pores.^[21]
3. **Acne Treatment:** Dab witch hazel directly onto blemishes with a cotton swab to help reduce redness and inflammation.^[21]
4. **Hair rinse:** Combine witch hazel with a bit of apple cider vinegar and water. Use it as a rinse after shampooing to help with a flaky scalp and add shine to hair.^[21]
5. **Shaving Soother:** Apply witch hazel after shaving to reduce irritation and soothe the skin.^[21]

CONCLUSION:

Witch hazel (*Hamamelis virginiana*) is a remarkable genus of plants celebrated for its unique seasonal characteristics, adaptability and versatility in both horticultural and medicinal contexts. It demonstrates a diverse range of applications and potential benefits, supported by both traditional use and emerging scientific evidence. Its astringents, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties make it a valuable ingredient in dermatological and cosmetic formulation. The

active compounds in Witch hazel, such as tannins and flavonoids, contribute to its astringent and anti-inflammatory effects. The variability in product formulations and quality further complicates standardization and effectiveness.

Traditional uses of Witch hazel span a broad spectrum, including the treatment of skin conditions like eczema and acne, and relief from haemorrhoids and minor wounds. These applications are supported by its ability to reduce inflammation and promote tissue healing. These shrubs are full of phytoconstituents, having natural goodness to fulfil the different demands of skin. Witch hazel (*Hamamelis virginiana*) underscores its multifaceted value across various domains, from traditional medicine to modern therapeutic applications. Its role in cosmetic formulations highlights its potential in improving skin health and reducing signs of aging.

Overall, Witch hazel stands out as a plant with substantial medicinal values, blending historical use with modern scientific validation. This comparative study demonstrates the role of dermo-cosmetics products tested not only as a support of treatment, but also as a first choice clinical approach.

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